

MECHANICAL AND THERMAL PROPERTIES OF HEATED COMPOSITE BOARD MADE OF WASTE OF CARBON FIBER

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ABSTRACT

The high-strength/lightweight heating composite board was tried to mold by extruding molding method. The waste of carbon fiber was used as a raw material for molding. And the recyclability of waste carbon fiber as reinforcement of CFRP was discussed in this paper. The strip-shaped composite board was obtained by extruding molding. The composites were heated by supplying the electric power to the carbon fibers from the edges of the specimen. The temperature of the composite was changed by regulate the electric power. The mechanical and thermal properties were examined by bending test for various temperature conditions. From the results, it was cleared that the bending strength and modulus increase with increasing the content of carbon fiber and decrease with increasing the temperature. It should be noted here that the bending properties of the composite heated by carbon fiber as heater are almost same as that for the composite set in the constant temperature chamber.

1 INTRODUCTION

To meet a wide variety of recent engineering requests, research has focused on the development of new materials. In particular, much attention has been focused upon developing of fiber-reinforced multifunctional composites such as CFRP (carbon fiber reinforced plastics). And also the attention has been shifting from thermosetting composites to thermoplastic composites because of the higher recyclability of thermoplastic matrix resins [1].

Meanwhile, increased emphasis has been placed on developing recycling techniques for industrial and post consumer wastes, with the goal of protecting the environment. For example, textile and plastic industries have taken a growing interest in developing a system for recycling the waste plastics (including composite materials) and textile products [2,3]. However, because of lack of effective recycling technique, most of these wastes are currently destroyed by fire or buried underground.

In the previous paper [4], we paid our attentions to the superior mechanical properties and good electrical conductivity of carbon fiber. And we tried to mold the high-strength/lightweight heating composite board by extruding molding from the waste of carbon fiber and PP (polypropylene). As a result, the carbon fiber reinforced the PP resin and enhanced the mechanical properties of obtained board. And also, with certain content of carbon fiber, the board became the electro conductive material. In this paper, in order to evaluate the obtained composite materials, the mechanical properties and thermal property were examined by bending test under the various temperature.

2 EXPERIMENTS

2.1 MOLDING MATERIALS

The amount of waste carbon fiber should increase rapidly because of the big spread of the application of CFRP. The waste carbon fiber mainly comes from the separation process of used CFRP into resin and fiber. And also the edge parts of the carbon fiber textile become the waste at the weaving process of textile. In this experiment, we used the cut waste of carbon fiber textile. Figure 1 shows the aspect of the carbon fiber used. The average length of carbon fiber is 52 mm. In general, the waste of carbon fiber is obtained as a state of discontinuous fiber and can be used as the reinforcement at the process of injection molding and extruding molding of composites. PP resin was used for the matrix material. In order to improve the adhesiveness between carbon fiber and PP, the maleic anhydride modified PP (Umex1001, Sanyo chemical industries, Ltd.) was also used.

2.2 MOLDING METHOD OF COMPOSITES

The cut waste of carbon fiber used here exists in the state of the fiber bundle. Then, in the molding process, the waste of carbon fiber was pre-treated by carding machine to make well-dispersed fiber web. The carbon fiber web and PP resin were mixed by kneading machine. Then the mixture was cooled and crushed to make mixed pellet. Figure 2 shows the aspect of mixed pellet. Then the mixed pellet was introduced in the extruding molding machine and the strip shaped carbon fiber/PP composite board was obtained. Figure 3 shows the aspect of composite board. The carbon fiber generates the heat by applying the voltage to the carbon fiber directly. However, as mentioned above, the carbon fiber is discontinuous in the composite. Therefore, there was a limit of carbon fiber contents for good heat generation property[4]. The content of carbon fiber was varied from 0wt% to 45wt% in the experiments to evaluate the relationship between material properties and the content of carbon fiber. Moreover, the samples in which 5wt% of Umex1001 is mixed at kneading process were also molded. Here, the carbon fiber in the board may shorten by shearing force during kneading and extruding process. So the length of carbon fiber in the molded board was measured by dissolving PP matrix of composite board by hot xylene and microscope measurement for 1000 fibers. Figure 4 shows the distribution of carbon fiber length in composite board. The average of fiber length was 77.8 μ m.

2.3 MECHANICAL PROPERTY AND HEAT GENERATION PROPERTY TESTS

The strip shaped carbon fiber/PP composite board was cut into the size of 200×19×4 mm and the bending properties were evaluated by three-point bending test with the span length of 32 mm and testing speed of 1.0 mm/min. for various temperatures.

The specimen was clumped by metal electrode with conductive grease or by solder. Then voltage was applied to the carbon fibers from both edges of specimen and electric current was measured by constant direct-current power supply system (DP-3005, CUSTOM corporation). In addition the temperature on the surface of specimen was measured by thermo camera (TH3102MR, NEC San'ei co. ltd.).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 MECHANICAL PROPERTIES IN ROOM TEMPERATURE

The relations between the content of carbon fiber (W_f) and bending strength (σ) and bending modulus (E) obtained in the previous paper[4] were shown in Figs.5(a) and (b), respectively. These figures indicate that σ and E increase with increasing W_f between 0~30wt%. And at 30~40wt% of W_f , the values of σ and E take maximum value. In special, it is notable that the value of σ increases extremely by using Umex1001. Therefore it is concluded here that the waste carbon fiber can be used for the composite as a good reinforcement.

3.2 HEAT GENERATION PROPERTY

Figures 6 and 7 show the effect of content of carbon fiber and content of Umex1001 on the surface temperature, respectively obtained by previous paper[4]. It was cleared that the surface temperature rises largely in the range of the fiber content over 30wt%. And also the temperature rises a little for

the composite with Umex1001. Therefore in this paper the thermal tests were carried out for the specimens in which the content of carbon fiber is over 35wt% and the content of Umex1001 is zero.

Figure 8 shows the typical image of surface temperature of specimen measured by thermo meter under the heated condition of 6W. It should be noted here that the temperature distributed in the surface and the lower temperature can be observed at the edge sides of the specimen.

Figure 9 shows the typical temperature profile along the longitudinal direction of specimen for the average temperature in each section of specimen. It is noted here that the average temperature rises with increasing the electric power and is almost same at the center area of the specimen. The difference of the temperature between max. and min. values such as $((\text{Max}-\text{Min})/\text{Max})$ was about 25% in this experiment.

Figure 10 shows the effect of electric power on the average surface temperature of the whole area of specimen of $W_f=35\text{wt}\%$. It is cleared here that the temperature rises almost linearly with increasing the electric power. As shown in Fig.8, the maximum temperature appear at the distance from the center of specimen. Therefore, the bending test was carried out under the condition in which the point of maximum temperature was set at the center of span length as shown in Fig.11.

Figure 12 shows the surface temperature distribution between both supporting points of three point bending test. It can be seen that the temperature takes almost same value along the longitudinal direction of specimen. The difference of the temperature between max. and min. values such as $((\text{Max}-\text{Min})/\text{Max})$ was about 10% in this experiments.

3.3 MECHANICAL PROPERTIES UNDER HEATING CONDITION

Figure 13 shows the bending stress-strain curves for the composite of $W_f=35\text{wt}\%$. Figure.14 also shows the bending stress-strain curves tested in the constant temperature chamber. As shown in these figures, the fairly ductile property appears for the cases of higher temperatures. It is noted here that the shape of S-S curves for both figures are almost similar each other.

Figures 15 and 16 show the effect of temperature on the bending strength and modulus, respectively. In these figures, the date obtained in the constant temperature chamber was also plotted. As shown in these figures, the bending strength and modulus decrease rapidly with increasing the temperature. It is noted here that the values of bending strength and modulus take almost same values for both heating methods. Therefore, it should be noted here that the bending property of the composite heated by applying the electric power to the carbon fiber can evaluate from the property of the composite tested in the constant temperature chamber.

4 CONCLUSION

In this research, high-strength/lightweight heating composite board was molded by extruding molding method by using the cut waste of carbon fiber as heat generating reinforcement. And the mechanical and thermal properties of composite board were examined by bending test and temperature measurement by infrared thermometer, respectively. The content of carbon fiber was varied from 0wt% to 45wt% in the experiments. The results obtained in the present paper can be summed up as follows.

- 1) The bending strength and modulus decreases rapidly with increasing the temperature.
- 2) The bending property of the composite heated by applying the electric power to the carbon fiber can evaluate from the property of the composite tested in the constant temperature chamber.
- 3) The molding methods described herein shows promise for contributing toward the material recycling of carbon fiber as a heat generation reinforcement of the composite material.

5 REFERENCES

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Fig. 1 Aspect of cut waste of carbon fiber

Fig.2 Carbon fiber/PP mixed pellet

Fig.3 Extruding molded Carbon fiber/PP composite material

Fig.4 Distribution of carbon fiber length in molded composite material

(a) Bending strength (b) Bending modulus
Fig.5 Bending strength and modulus of molded composite materials

Fig.6 Effect of content of carbon fiber on surface temperature of molded composite

Fig.7 Effect of content of Umex1001 on surface temperature of molded composite

Fig.8 Typical image of surface temperature of molded composite (6W)

Fig.9 Temperature profile along the longitudinal direction of heated composite ($W_f=35\text{wt}\%$)

Fig.10 Relation between electric power and average surface temperature ($W_f=35\text{wt}\%$)

Fig.11 Condition of bending test

Fig.12 Temperature distribution between both supporting points of bending test ($W_f=35\text{wt}\%$)

Fig.13 Bending stress-strain curve ($W_f=35\text{wt}\%$)

Fig.14 Bending stress-strain curve tested in constant temperature chamber ($W_f=35\text{wt}\%$)

Fig.15 Effect of temperature on bending strength ($W_f=35\text{wt}\%$)

Fig.16 Effect of temperature on bending modulus ($W_f=35\text{wt}\%$)